

A tale of two vesicles: Niosomes vs proniosomes: comparative review

D. Vinay kumar, K. Srinivas Reddy, Baby. Surla, Velnati kiran kumar

ABSTRACT: Niosomes and proniosomes, vesicular carriers composed of non-ionic surfactants, have gained significant attention in drug delivery due to their biocompatibility, versatility, and potential for targeted drug delivery. This comparative review delves into the structural, functional, and application aspects of these promising delivery systems. Niosomes are self-assembled, spherical vesicles with a bilayer membrane composed of non-ionic surfactants, often incorporating cholesterol for structural stability. Proniosomes, on the other hand, are precursor to niosomes, existing as dry, lamellar structures that hydrate to form niosomes upon contact with aqueous media. This review highlights the distinct characteristics of niosomes and proniosomes, including their formation mechanisms, size distribution, encapsulation efficiency, and release profiles. We delve into the advantages and limitations of each system, comparing their stability, drug loading capacity, and potential for targeted drug delivery. Furthermore, this review explores the diverse applications of niosomes and proniosomes in various therapeutic fields, including topical drug delivery, transdermal drug delivery, and vaccine development. The review concludes by highlighting current research trends and future directions in the field, emphasizing the ongoing efforts to enhance the efficacy and safety of these promising drug delivery platforms. By comparing the advantages of niosomes and proniosomes, this review provides a comprehensive overview of these systems for researchers and practitioners seeking innovative approaches to drug delivery.

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving landscape of drug delivery, where innovation strives to bridge the gap between therapeutic promise and clinical reality, niosomes and proniosomes emerge as two versatile contenders. These microscopic delivery systems, each with their unique architecture and properties, encapsulate therapeutic agents, shielding them from degradation while navigating the intricate biological environment to reach their target sites with enhanced efficiency. While sharing a common goal to improve drug delivery and therapeutic outcomes of niosomes and proniosomes differ in their composition, preparation methods, stability profiles, and release kinetics, making the choice between them a nuanced decision based on the specific drug and intended application.⁽¹⁾

NIOSOMES

Niosomes, derived from the Greek word "nios" (meaning vesicle) and "soma" (meaning body), are self-assembled, non-ionic surfactant-based vesicles that encapsulate drugs within their aqueous core or lipid bilayer. These microscopic spheres, typically ranging from 10 nanometers to a few micrometers in size, offer a versatile platform for delivering a wide range of therapeutic agents, including small molecules, peptides, proteins, and even nucleic acids.

The appeal of niosomes as drug delivery vehicles stems from their unique ability to enhance drug solubility and bioavailability, control drug release, and minimize drug degradation. Composed primarily of non-ionic surfactants, cholesterol, and sometimes charged molecules. Niosomes exhibit biocompatibility, low toxicity, and relative ease of preparation.⁽²⁾

The structural foundation of niosomes lies in the self-assembly of non-ionic surfactants in aqueous solutions. These surfactants, characterized by their hydrophilic head groups and hydrophobic tail groups, spontaneously arrange themselves to minimize contact between the hydrophobic tails and the surrounding water molecules. This self-assembly process, driven by thermodynamic principles, results in the formation of bilayered vesicles, with the hydrophilic head groups oriented towards the aqueous environments both inside and outside the vesicle, and the hydrophobic tails sequestered within the bilayer, forming a barrier similar nature to cell membranes.⁽³⁾

Cholesterol, a key component in niosome formulations, inserts within the surfactant bilayer, modulating membrane fluidity and enhancing vesicle stability. The inclusion of charged molecules, such as dicetyl

phosphate or stearylamine, can further tailor the surface charge of niosomes, influencing their interaction with biological membranes and their overall pharmacokinetic behavior.⁽⁴⁾

PRONIOSOMES

Addressing the limitations of niosome stability, proniosomes have emerged as an ingenious alternative. Proniosomes, as their name suggests, are essentially "pro-niosomes" are dry, free-flowing formulations that readily convert into niosomes upon hydration. These shelf-stable precursor, composed of carrier molecules like sorbitol or maltodextrin coated with surfactant monomers, offer enhanced stability, ease of handling, and the advantage of on-demand niosome formation.⁽³⁴⁾

The defining characteristic of proniosomes lies in their remarkable ability to transform from dry, free-flowing powders into niosomes, those microscopic drug-delivery vehicles, upon contact with water. This process, known as hydration, is the key that unlocks the therapeutic potential encapsulated within these ingenious formulations.

Imagine sprinkling proniosome powder into water. The water molecules, tiny but mighty, penetrate the dry particle matrix, seeking out the water-soluble carrier molecules coating the surfactant monomers. As the carrier dissolves, it relinquishes its hold on the surfactant molecules, setting the stage for a spontaneous self-assembly process.⁽⁵⁾

Freed from their carrier embrace, the surfactant molecules, driven by their inherent tendency to minimize contact between their hydrophobic tails and the surrounding water, arrange themselves into bilayered vesicles – niosomes. This elegant dance of molecules, dictated by the laws of thermodynamics, results in the formation of countless microscopic spheres, each encapsulating a portion of the drug payload within their aqueous core or lipid bilayer.

The hydration process, however, is not a simple phenomenon where the rate and extent of hydration, and consequently, the characteristics of the resulting niosomes, are influenced by a delicate interplay of factors. Temperature, agitation, the composition of the hydration medium, and the specific formulation of the proniosome all play pivotal roles in shaping the size, lamellarity, and drug encapsulation efficiency of the final product. This tunability, this ability to fine-tune the hydration process, empowers researchers to exert precise control over the properties and behavior of the resulting niosomes, tailoring them for specific therapeutic applications.⁽⁶⁾

Figures of Niosomes & Proniosomes

Fig No.:1

STRUCTURE AND COMPOSITION

Niosomes	Proniosomes
<p>A general niosomal vesicle consists of amphiphilic forming vesicle i.e non ionic surfactant, cholesterol and small amount of anionic surfactant. In that cholesterol and non ionic surfactant are main components used to produce niosomes.⁽⁷⁾</p>	<p>Proniosomes are microscopic lamellar structures, composed of non-ionic surfactant of the alkyl or dialkyl polyglycerol ether and cholesterol followed by hydration in aqueous medium.^(9,10)</p>
Structure	
<p>fig No.:2</p>	<p>fig No.:3</p>
Components	
<p>1. Non-ionic surfactants: Examples: ✓ Alkyl ethers and alkyl glyceryl ethers: Polyoxyethylene 4 lauryl ether, polyoxyethylenecetyl ethers ✓ sorbiton fatty acid esters: Span 80,60,40,20 ✓ Polyoxyethylene fatty acidesters: Tween 80,60,40,20 ✓ Block copolymers Criteria for selection: ✓ HLB value: should be between 1.7-8.6. Entrapment efficiency is inversely proportional to HLB value. ✓ Critical packing parameter: CPP=volume of hydrophobic group/critical hydrophobic group length (lc)× area of polar head group (a0) CPP value should be between ½ to 1. ✓ Transition temperature (Tc): Transition temperature is directly proportional to the entrapment efficiency.</p>	<p>1. Surfactant: Especially non-ionic surfactants are important in the production of proniosomes. Examples: ✓ Alkyl ethers and alkyl glyceryl ethers: Polyoxyethylene 4 lauryl ether, polyoxyethylenecetyl ethers, polyoxyethylene stearyl ethers ✓ sorbiton fatty acid esters: Span 80,60,40,20 ✓ Polyoxyethylene fatty acidesters: Tween 80,60,40,20 Criteria for selection: ✓ HLB value: should be between 4 to 8 for formation of vesicles. ✓ Critical packing parameter: CPP=volume of hydrophobic group/critical hydrophobic group length (lc)× area of polar head group (a0) The drug entrapment efficiency is influenced by non-ionic surfactants hydrophilic head group chain length and size. ✓ Transition temperature (Tc): Transition temperature is directly proportional to the entrapment efficiency</p>
<p>2. Cholesterol: Steroids are important components of the cell</p>	<p>2.cholesterol:</p>

<p>membrane which have impact on bilayer fluidity and permeability. As cholesterol is a steroid derivative it is used to provide rigidity, proper shape and confirmation to noisomal preparation. Cholesterol stabilizes the system against the formation of aggregates by repulsive steric or electrostatic forces that leads to transition from gel to liquid phase in noisome system.</p>	<p>Cholesterol interact with non-ionic detergents to modulate the physical and structural properties of proniosomes.</p> <p>Depending on the HLB value of detergent the amount of cholesterol required was determined.</p>
<p>3. Additives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Charge inducers: To increase the physical stability, to hinder vesicle agglomeration by electrostatic repulsive forces. Examples: diethyl phosphate and phosphatidic acid, stearyl amine, stearlypyridinium chloride and cetylpyridinium chloride bearing a positive charge. ✓ Cationic/ helper lipids: elaboration of Niosomes as gene Delivery platform. ✓ Polyethylene glycol: elaboration of stealth Niosomes. 	<p>3. lecithin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Lecithin is a phospholipid that acts as a membrane stabilizer. Examples: soyabean and egg lecithin and hydrated types of lecithin The double bond in uncured lecithin allow the molecular chain to bend and prevent intimate contact with neighbouring molecules. This makes membrane less stiff and more permeable.
<p>Types:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Multi Lamellar Vesicles- size (>0.05μm) 2. Large Unilamellar Vesicles-size (>0.10μm) 3. Small Unilamellar Vesicles (0.025-0.05μm)^(7,8) 	<p>4. hydration medium: Phosphate buffer (PH 7.4), 0.1% glycerol and hot water are primarily used as hydration medium. PH of hydration medium has impact on the entrapment efficiency. Drug encapsulation increased as the PH lowered from 8 to 5.5. As PH drops, the unionised flurbiprofen species, have higher partitioning to bilayer lipid phase than ionised species.</p> <p>5. organic solvent: Choice solvent has has significant impact on vesicle size and drug permeability. Size of vesicle and drug permeability depends on type of alcohol used. Order: ethanol>propanol>butanol>Isopropanol</p> <p>6. carrier material: Carrier materials were used to hold the drug in the proniosomes. Examples: sorbitol, mannitol.</p> <p>Types:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dry granular <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Sorbitol based b. Maldextrin based 2. Liquid crystalline^(9,10)

Table :1**PREPARATION METHODS**

Niosomes	Proniosomes
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● THIN FILM HYDRATION TECHNIQUE (TFH)/HAND SHAKING METHOD● BUBBLE METHOD● ETHER INJECTION METHOD (EIM)● SONICATION METHOD(SON)● REVERSE PHASE EVAPORATION TECHNIQUE (RPE)● MICROFLUDIZATION METHOD● HEATING METHOD● FREEZ AND THAW METHOD● PRONIOSOME TECHNOLOGY● ENZYMATIC METHOD● SINGLE-PASS METHOD● HANDJANI-VIA METHOD⁽¹¹⁾	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● SLURRY METHOD● SLOW SPRAY COATING METHOD● COASERVATION SPRAY METHOD^(12,13)

NIOSOMES:⁽¹⁴⁾

Flow chart:1

PRNOSOMES:⁽⁸⁾

Flow chart:2

CHARACTERIZATION TECHNIQUES OF BOTH NIOSOMES AND PRONIOSOMES

Niosomes composed of non-ionic surfactants and often incorporating cholesterol, encapsulate drugs within their bilayered structure, offering advantages such as enhanced drug encapsulation, prolonged release, targeted delivery, and improved bioavailability. Proniosomes, on the other hand, are considered the precursor to niosomes, existing as a dry, solid form that can be readily reconstituted into niosomes upon hydration. This unique feature makes proniosomes particularly attractive for applications where stability and ease of handling are crucial.

While both niosomes and proniosomes share the common goal of delivering drugs effectively, their distinct structural features and formation processes necessitate a subtle approach to characterization. Understanding their specific properties and differences is critical for optimizing their formulation and ensuring their suitability for diverse therapeutic applications. This comprehensive exploration delves into the multifaceted world of niosome and proniosome characterization, comparing and contrasting techniques used to unravel their distinct characteristics..^(15,16)

SIZE AND MORPHOLOGY

The size and morphology of niosomes and proniosomes are fundamental parameters that govern their interactions with biological systems. These characteristics influence their ability to penetrate biological barriers, interact with cells, and deliver the encapsulated payload to the target site. Generally the size of the niosome and proniosome particles varies from about 10 nm to about 50 μm .^(17,18,19)

DYNAMIC LIGHT SCATTERING (DLS)

This non-invasive technique, also known as photon correlation spectroscopy, measures the size distribution of particles in a suspension by analyzing the scattering of light. DLS provides a rapid and convenient method to determine the mean size and size distribution of niosomes and proniosomes in solution. A narrow size distribution is generally desirable, as it ensures a more consistent and predictable release profile. For instance, DLS might reveal that niosomes have a mean diameter of 100 nm with a narrow size distribution, indicating good uniformity and potential for targeted drug delivery. In contrast, proniosomes, existing in a dry form, cannot be directly analyzed using DLS. However, DLS can be used to assess the size distribution of niosomes reconstituted from proniosomes, providing valuable insights into the reconstitution process.⁽²⁰⁾

ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (SEM AND TEM):

Electron microscopy techniques provide high-resolution images of niosomes and proniosomes, revealing their surface morphology and internal structures. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) uses a focused beam of electrons to scan the surface of a sample, producing detailed images of the niosome's external morphology. This technique helps determine the shape, size, and surface texture of the niosomes, providing valuable insights into their interaction with biological systems. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) employs a beam of electrons that passes through the sample, providing information about the niosome's internal structures, including the presence of multilamellar structures or internal compartments. SEM might reveal spherical or lamellar niosomes, influencing their biodistribution and cellular uptake, while TEM might visualize drug-laden structures, providing insights into encapsulation efficiency and release mechanisms. Proniosomes, being a solid form, are typically not directly visualized using TEM due to their solid nature. However, TEM can be used to visualize the niosomes reconstituted from proniosomes, providing insights into the morphology of the reconstituted niosomes.^(21,22,23)

SURFACE CHARGE

The surface charge of niosomes and proniosomes, measured as their zeta potential, plays a crucial role in their stability and interactions with biological systems. The zeta potential represents the electrical potential difference between the particle surface and the surrounding medium.

ZETA POTENTIAL MEASUREMENT:

This measurement is typically performed using a technique called electrophoresis, where niosomes and proniosomes are subjected to an electric field. The speed at which the particles migrate under the influence of the electric field is proportional to their zeta potential. A higher zeta potential, either positive or negative, generally indicates greater stability and reduced aggregation. This is because the repulsive forces between particles with similar surface charges prevent them from clumping together.

The surface charge of niosomes and proniosomes can be strategically adjusted by modifying the composition of the lipid bilayer. For instance, incorporating charged surfactants or incorporating charged molecules can alter the overall surface charge. The surface charge of niosomes and proniosomes can be manipulated to improve their stability, target them to specific cell types, or enhance their interaction with biological molecules. For example, negatively charged niosomes might exhibit better stability in biological fluids compared to neutral or positively charged niosomes. This is because the negative charge helps to repel them from other negatively charged surfaces, such as those found on red blood cells, leading to improved circulation time and reduced opsonization. Proniosomes, due to their solid nature, may exhibit different surface charge characteristics compared to niosomes. However, understanding the zeta potential of the reconstituted niosomes is crucial for assessing their stability and interactions with biological systems.⁽²⁴⁾

DRUG LOADING

Encapsulation efficiency (EE) represents the percentage of drug successfully loaded into the niosomes or proniosomes during the formulation process. It is a critical parameter, as it directly influences the therapeutic efficacy of the formulation. High EE is essential for delivering a sufficient amount of drug to the target site and achieving the desired therapeutic effect.^(19,25)

Analytical Techniques for Determining EE: Various analytical techniques are employed to quantify EE, including

High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC): HPLC separates and quantifies the drug from the niosome or proniosome formulation. This technique offers high sensitivity and accuracy, enabling precise determination of the amount of drug encapsulated within the niosomes or proniosomes.⁽²⁶⁾

Ultraviolet-Visible (UV-Vis) Spectroscopy: UV-Vis spectroscopy utilizes the absorbance of light at specific wavelengths to quantify the drug concentration in the niosome or proniosome formulation. It is a relatively simple and rapid method for quantifying the drug concentration, although its sensitivity may be lower than HPLC.⁽⁵⁾

By accurately determining EE, researchers can optimize the formulation process to maximize drug loading and minimize drug loss during the preparation and storage of niosomes and proniosomes. For instance, an EE of 80% for a particular drug would indicate that 80% of the initial drug added during formulation is encapsulated within the niosomes or proniosomes, ensuring a high drug concentration for effective therapeutic delivery.⁽²⁷⁾

Drug release kinetics

Drug release kinetics describe the pattern of drug liberation from the niosomes or proniosomes over time. This is a crucial aspect of characterization, as it dictates the duration of drug action, the therapeutic window, and the targeting capabilities of the formulation.⁽⁵⁾

In Vitro Release Studies:

These studies simulate the release process under controlled laboratory conditions. Common methods include:

Dialysis Membrane Technique: A dialysis membrane separates the niosome or proniosome formulation from a release medium, mimicking the conditions in the body. The drug concentration in the release medium is measured at different time points, providing data on the release profile.⁽²⁹⁾

Dissolution Testing: This technique employs a dissolution apparatus to mimic the gastrointestinal tract or other physiological environments. The drug release rate is determined by analyzing the drug concentration in the dissolution medium at various time points.⁽³⁰⁾

By studying the release kinetics, researchers can optimize the formulation to achieve sustained release, targeted delivery, or rapid drug release, depending on the specific therapeutic requirements. For example, a sustained-release formulation might aim to provide a slow, gradual release of the drug over an extended period, minimizing frequent dosing and improving patient compliance. Conversely, a rapid-release formulation might be designed for immediate action, such as in emergency situations.⁽³¹⁾

Proniosomes, in their dry, solid form, typically exhibit no drug release until they are reconstituted into niosomes. In vitro release studies are therefore conducted after the reconstitution of proniosomes into niosomes, providing insights into the release profile of the reconstituted niosomes.⁽³²⁾

STABILITY STUDIES:

Stability studies are conducted under controlled conditions to evaluate the niosomes and proniosomes ability to maintain their physical and chemical characteristics. These studies involve storing formulations under different conditions, such as:

Temperature Stability: Niosomes and proniosomes are stored at different temperatures (e.g: 4°C, 25°C, 40°C) to assess their resistance to temperature fluctuations.⁽³³⁾

Humidity Stability: Niosomes and proniosomes are exposed to different humidity levels to assess their sensitivity to moisture.⁽³⁴⁾

pH Stability: Niosomes and proniosomes are subjected to different pH values to evaluate their stability in different biological environments.

The results of these studies provide valuable information about the shelf life of the formulations, the appropriate storage conditions and the suitability of the formulation for different applications. For example, a stability study might reveal that proniosomes remain stable for at least six months when stored at 4°C, indicating a reasonable shelf life for pharmaceutical use.

Proniosomes, due to their dry, solid nature, often exhibit superior stability compared to niosomes. This makes them particularly attractive for applications where long term storage is essential, such as in remote areas or for emergency preparedness.⁽³⁵⁾

DRUGS INCORPORATED INTO NIOSOMES^(36,8) & PRONIOSOMES^(36,37)

Sl. No.	Drugs	Uses
1.	Methotrexate	Anticancer
2.	Paclitaxel	Anticancer
3.	Curcumin	Anticancer, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory
4.	Acetazolamide	Glaucoma
5.	Rifampicin	Anti tubercular , antimicrobial
6.	Sodium stibogluconate	Visceral, mucosal leishmaniasis
7.	Vinblastin	Anticancer
8.	Tetanus toxoid	Tetanus
9.	Embelin	Anti-diabetic
10.	Ganciclovir	Herpes viruses: varicella-zoster virus, cytomegalovirus, and Epstein-Barr virus
11.	Minoxidil	Androgenetic alopecia
12.	Nystatin	Fungal infection
13.	Letrozole	Anticancer
14.	Diallyl disulfide	Antibacterial antifungal
15.	Morin hydrate (MH)	Antimicrobial and anticancer
16.	Ellagic acid (EA)	Antioxidant
17.	Topotecan	Antitumor
18.	Hydroxy chloroquine	Rheumatoid arthritis

Table No:2

Sl. No.	Drugs	Uses
1.	Piroxicam	Anti-inflammatory
2.	Levonorgestrel	Contraceptive agent
3.	Ketorolac	Anti-inflammatory
4.	Ibuprofen	Anti-inflammatory
5.	Ethinylestradiol and levonorgestrel	Contraception and hormone replacement therapy
6.	Frusemide	Antihypertensive
7.	Flurbiprofen	Anti-inflammatory
8.	Estradiol	Hormonal insufficiencies
9.	Cromolyn sodium	Anti-asthmatic and anti-allergic
10.	Chlorpheniramine maleate	Anti-allergic
11.	Captopril	Hypertension
12.	Aceclofenac	Arthritis, ankylosing spondylitis
13.	Brimonidine tartarate	Glaucoma treatment
14.	Budesonide	Anti-asthmatic agent
15.	Duloxetine	Anti-depressant
16.	Lornoxicam	Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug
17.	Curcumin	Neutraceutical
18.	Letrozole	Anti-cancer agent

Table No:3

CONVERSION OF NIOSOMES TO PRONIOSOMES

Niosomes, tiny spherical vesicles with an aqueous core, are efficient drug delivery systems. However, their inherent fragility and limited stability pose challenges in handling and storage. To overcome these limitations, a clever strategy involves transforming niosomes into their dehydrated precursors, known as proniosomes. This conversion involves a controlled drying process, carefully removing water from the niosome's core. As the water evaporates, the core solidifies into a stable, solid matrix. While the outer layer, composed of specialized molecules, adjusts to form a protective barrier around the dehydrated core. The resulting proniosomes are robust, stable, and easily handled, allowing for convenient storage and transportation. This transformation process is reversible; upon rehydration with an aqueous medium. Proniosomes rapidly revert to their niosomal form, regaining their ability to deliver their precious cargo. This dynamic conversion between niosomes and proniosomes offers a versatile approach to drug delivery, balancing stability and controlled release. ^(38,39,40)

fig No.:4

CONVERSION OF PROIOSOMES TO NIOSOMES

Proniosomes, the dehydrated precursors to niosomes, exist in a stable, solid form, awaiting activation. These tiny, dry packages, containing a precious cargo within a solid matrix, are carefully crafted for controlled release. Upon contact with an aqueous environment, a remarkable transformation occurs. Water molecules, drawn to the dehydrated core to penetrate the protective barrier, rehydrating the matrix. This influx of water causes the core to soften and expand, returning to its fluid state. The outer layer, comprised of specialized molecules, responds dynamically, reorganizing and reforming around the rehydrated core. This rapid hydration process results in the formation of niosomes, spherical vesicles with an aqueous core ready to deliver their cargo. The conversion from proniosome to niosome is a remarkable process, offering advantages like improved stability, ease of handling, and the potential for controlled drug release. This transformation enables efficient and adaptable drug delivery systems. ⁽⁴¹⁾

fig No.: 5

ADVANTAGES

Niosomes^(42,43,44)

1. Improve solubility and bioavailability of some poorly soluble drugs.
Ex: Acyclovir and Griseofulvin
2. Improve stability of drug delivery during storage.
Ex: stability of peptide drugs
3. By altering the vesicle characteristics such as vesicle composition, size, lamellarity, tapped volume and surface charge, a desired niosomes can be prepared.
4. Both lipophilic and hydrophilic, amphiphilic drugs can be encapsulated into niosomes.
5. Niosomes can be administrated by various routes like oral, parenteral and topical. There is no issue of irritation and damage caused by penetration enhancers in ocular drug delivery system.

Proniosomes^(45,46,39)

1. The drawbacks of niosomes fusion, aggregation, sedimentation, leakage of entrapped drugs, loss of vesicular integrity are overcome by proniosomes.
2. The non-ionic surfactants and phospholipids in proniosomes helps to medication diffusion and enhance permeation to targeted areas and reduce toxic effects.
3. Proniosomes can be formulated as anhydrous free flowing formulations or liquid crystals with jelly like consistency of water soluble carrier coated with surfactants.
4. These are also called as “dry niosomes” which are easy to transport, distribution and storage.
5. By adding aqueous phase before administration or hydrated in body compartments proniosomes can be easily reconstituted to niosomes, these proniosomes derived niosomes are better than conventional niosomes.

APPLICATIONS OF NIOSOMES & PRONIOSOMES

1. Drug carriers

- Used as iobitridol carriers in X-ray imaging.
- Used as carriers of radiopharmaceuticals.
Ex: 99mTc labelled DTPA containing niosomes used for liver and spleen imaging studies.
- In case of transdermal drug delivery systems niosomes serves as solubilization matrix for modulation of systemic absorption of drugs.
Ex: 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) (by using thin layer evaporation technique^(47,48))

2. Carriers for haemoglobin

Niosomes can be used as carrier for Haemoglobin. Hence niosomal formulations containing haemoglobin can be used to treat anemia, which was found to give superimposable curve on free haemoglobin curve.^(47,48,7)

3. Immune response

Niosomes are used to study the immune response by antigens. Antigens and peptides are formulated as non-ionic surfactant vesicles for parenteral administration.⁽⁴⁹⁾

4. Ophthalmic drug delivery

Niosomal formulations of drugs shows variation in the release rate, and exhibit sluggish release.
Ex: Estradiol, Gentamicin sulphate, timolol maleate (0.25%).⁽⁴⁹⁾

5. Neoplasia

The anthracyclic antibiotic such as Doxorubicin which shows broad spectrum anti-tumour activity shows dose depend antirreversible cardio toxic effect. Niosomal formulation of Doxorubicin when administered to mice bearing S- 180 tumor shows increased their life span and rate of proliferation of sarcoma was decreased. In the similar way methotrexate when administered intravenously to mice bearing S-180 tumor shows regression of tumor and increased plasma level concentration.^(7,49)

6. Leishmaniasis

Leishmaniasis which is disease caused by parasite of genus Leishmania which invades the liver cells and spleen cells. Antimonial drugs used to treat this disease but at higher concentrations they damage heart,

liver and kidney as they are related to arsenic. Use of niosomes to administer shows higher level of drug without triggering side effects and thus shows greater efficacy in treatment.⁽⁴⁹⁾

7. Transdermal drug delivery

In transdermal drug delivery system permeation of the drug through the skin is the major drawback and this can be avoided by incorporating drug into niosomes, which increases the rate of penetration. Topical niosomes act as local depot for sustained release of dermally active compounds, which may serve as solubilizing matrix.⁽⁵⁰⁾

8. Gene delivery

To overcome the limitations in gene therapy and to improve the transfection efficiency multifunctional niosomes have been used.

Ex: magnetic cationic niosomes were used as a delivery platform for Lifeguard (LFG)- specific siRNA inside the hydrophilic niosomal core.

Super-paramagnetic iron oxide nano particles were incorporated into niosomal bilayer structure during preparation in order to increase the cellular uptake via external magnetic field and then siRNA loading was carried out.⁽⁵¹⁾

9. In cosmetics

Niosomal delivery increases the stability of entrapped drugs, improved bioavailability of poorly absorbed ingredients and enhanced skin permeation.

Niosomes for delivery of antioxidants and whitening ingredients. For example turmeric contains curcuminoids which are bioactive compounds with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer properties which is encapsulated in niosomes to increase skin permeation and which shows 83% of encapsulation.

Niosomes for delivery of anti-scarring ingredients: elastic fabricated niosome particles have ability to increase the chemical stability and transdermal penetration of gallic acid which is carrier for skin-ageing compound and in the similar way black tea which is used as skin antioxidant which is encapsulated in niosomes using film hydration method.^(51,60)

10. Delivery of peptide drugs

Oral delivery of peptides have drawbacks like by passing the enzymes which causes breakdown of peptides. Entrapment of peptides into niosomes shows increased stability of peptides.⁽⁵²⁾

11. Vaccine delivery

Vaccine carrier system formulations were based on non-ionic surfactant vesicles. Skin has potential alternative route for non-invasive delivery of vaccine. In topical immunization introduction of antigen through topical application onto intact skin has many advantages compared to injectable route of administration.

Example: elastic vesicle transferosomes, non-ionic surfactant vesicles and liposomes were used in non-invasive delivery of tetanus toxoid (TT).⁽⁵³⁾

12. Brain targeting

Niosomal formulation of vasoactive intestinal peptide for brain targeted delivery. In this radiolabelled (I125) VIP- loaded glucosebearing niosomes were injected to mice intravenously. Which exhibits higher VIP brain uptake as compared to control.⁽⁵⁴⁾

13. Drug targeting:

Proniosomes have ability target drugs to Reticulo- endothelial system (RES). The uptake of proniosomes is controlled by opsonins which are useful for niosome clearance. proniosomes were used to target the liver and spleen in case of liver, spleen tumours and also in case of parasitic infection of liver.⁽⁵⁵⁾

CHALLENGES OF NIOSOMES

One of the most significant challenges lies in enhancing niosome stability. Niosomes are prone to degradation due to factors such as temperature fluctuations, pH changes and the presence of certain chemicals. This instability can impact their efficacy and shelf life, making it crucial to develop robust formulations that can withstand environmental stresses and maintain their integrity over time. This can involve exploring novel stabilizing agents, optimizing the composition of the niosomal membrane and developing protective coatings to shield them from degradation. For instance, incorporating polymers with pH-sensitive properties into the niosomal membrane could enhance their stability under different physiological conditions.⁽⁵⁶⁾

Furthermore, controlling the size and morphology of niosomes is critical for their effective delivery. The size of niosomes influences their pharmacokinetic behavior and cellular uptake, while their morphology impacts their stability and encapsulation efficiency. Developing consistent and reliable methods for control these parameters is vital for achieving predictable and reproducible results. This could involve investigating new techniques for niosome formation, such as microfluidic methods, which can offer precise control over size and morphology. Utilizing techniques like extrusion or sonication under controlled conditions could also be explored to achieve the desired size distribution and morphology.⁽⁵⁷⁾

Additionally, optimizing the encapsulation efficiency of niosomes remains a challenge. Ensuring that the therapeutic agent is effectively encapsulated within the niosome structure is crucial for maximizing its delivery to the target site. Factors influencing encapsulation efficiency include the physicochemical properties of the drug, the composition of the niosome, and the preparation method. Developing strategies to enhance encapsulation efficiency while maintaining the integrity of the niosomes is a key area of focus for future research. This could involve exploring novel encapsulating materials, optimizing the loading process, and employing techniques like co-encapsulation to enhance drug loading and stability. For example, incorporating specific lipids or polymers with high drug affinity could enhance encapsulation efficiency. Beyond these fundamental challenges, scaling up niosome production to meet the demands of clinical trials and commercialization is crucial. While laboratory-scale production methods have been developed, scaling up these processes to ensure consistency, reproducibility, and cost-effectiveness is crucial for their successful translation. This requires the development of robust and scalable manufacturing technologies that can produce high-quality niosomes on a large scale while maintaining their stability and desired characteristics. This could involve exploring continuous manufacturing processes, utilizing advanced technologies like microfluidics, or employing controlled crystallization techniques to improve scalability and reproducibility.

Another significant challenge lies in characterizing the complex structure and properties of niosomes. Their intricate structure and dynamic nature make it difficult to fully characterize their properties using conventional techniques. Developing novel and sophisticated analytical tools is essential to accurately determine the size distribution, morphology, encapsulation efficiency, and release kinetics of niosomes. This information is critical for optimizing their design and ensuring their predictable performance *in vivo*. This could involve employing advanced imaging techniques, such as atomic force microscopy or cryogenic electron microscopy, to visualize niosomes in detail. Furthermore, utilizing sophisticated analytical tools, such as dynamic light scattering, and advanced spectroscopy methods could provide detailed insights into their properties and behavior.

Finally, bridging the gap between preclinical studies and clinical trials is essential for translating niosomes into effective therapies. This involves addressing regulatory hurdles, conducting robust clinical trials to establish safety and efficacy in humans, and developing clear and concise guidelines for their clinical application. Furthermore, understanding the interaction of niosomes with the biological environment is crucial for optimizing their design and ensuring their safe and effective application. This involves studying their interactions with cells, tissues, and the immune system to predict their potential effects and minimize any adverse reactions. Developing *in vitro* and *in vivo* models that mimic the biological environment could provide valuable insights into niosome biodistribution, clearance, and potential interactions with the immune system.

Overcoming these challenges requires a multidisciplinary approach involving collaboration between researchers in pharmaceuticals, materials science, engineering, and clinical medicine. By addressing these challenges,

niosomes hold immense potential to transform therapeutic strategies by enabling targeted drug delivery, controlled release, and enhanced efficacy.⁽⁵⁸⁾

CHALLENGES OF PRNIOSOMES

One of the most significant challenges lies in enhancing proniosome stability. Proniosomes are prone to degradation due to factors such as temperature fluctuations, pH changes, and the presence of certain chemicals. This instability can impact their efficacy and shelf life, making it crucial to develop robust formulations that can withstand environmental stresses and maintain their integrity over time. Moreover, controlling the size and morphology of proniosomes is critical for their effective delivery. The size of proniosomes influences their pharmacokinetic behavior and cellular uptake, while their morphology impacts their stability and encapsulation efficiency⁽⁵⁹⁾. Developing consistent and reliable methods for controlling these parameters is vital for achieving predictable and reproducible results. Furthermore, optimizing the encapsulation efficiency of proniosomes remains a challenge. Ensuring that the therapeutic agent is effectively encapsulated within the proniosome structure is crucial for maximizing its delivery to the target site⁽⁶⁰⁾. Factors influencing encapsulation efficiency include the physicochemical properties of the drug, the composition of the proniosome, and the preparation method. Developing strategies to enhance encapsulation efficiency while maintaining the integrity of the proniosomes is a key area of focus for future research. Beyond these fundamental challenges, scaling up proniosome production to meet the demands of clinical trials and commercialization is crucial. While laboratory-scale production methods have been developed, scaling up these processes to ensure consistency, reproducibility, and cost-effectiveness is crucial for their successful translation. This requires the development of robust and scalable manufacturing technologies that can produce high-quality proniosomes on a large scale while maintaining their stability and desired characteristics. Another significant challenge lies in characterizing the complex structure and properties of proniosomes⁽³⁴⁾. Their intricate structure and dynamic nature make it difficult to fully characterize their properties using conventional techniques. Developing novel and sophisticated analytical tools is essential to accurately determine the size distribution, morphology, encapsulation efficiency, and release kinetics of proniosomes. This information is critical for optimizing their design and ensuring their predictable performance *in vivo*.⁽⁶⁰⁾

CONCLUSION

Niosomes and proniosomes offer distinct advantages as versatile drug delivery systems. While niosomes provide immediate drug release and greater stability, proniosomes offer ease of preparation, storage stability, and controlled drug release. Both systems exhibit excellent biocompatibility and the potential for targeted delivery. Ongoing research continues to optimize their formulation, enhance drug loading efficiency, and explore novel applications. By carefully considering the specific needs of the drug and the desired delivery profile, researchers can choose the most suitable niosome or proniosome formulation to maximize therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance.

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